

Participant information sheet

Information for participants in the PhD project "*Integrating Digital Literacy and Open Process Documentation as Design Practices to Support Urban Manufacturing*"

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1 Introduction

This information sheet¹ explains the qualitative research carried out as part of the PhD project "*Integrating Digital Literacy and Open Process Documentation as Design Practices to Support Urban Manufacturing*". You are invited to take part in this research by taking part in a study where we ask you questions. This involves the following:

- A one-to-one interview
- A study where researchers watch what happens and take notes referenced as observational study
- A study where you keep a diary referenced as diary study

This document will tell you everything you need to know to decide whether you want to take part in the study or not. Matteo Subet is the person in charge of the research, known as Principal Investigator or PI. The PI works with the Universitat de Vic – Universitat Central de Catalunya (UVic-UCC) at the Elisava, Barcelona School of Design and Engineering. Also, the PI is a member of the Interaction Design research group at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI).

2 Background

This research looks at how digital tools can help to capture and share knowledge in the manufacturing sector. As cities try to bring back small-scale and sustainable production, it becomes more important to have good records. Well-written documents help turn individual practices into shared, reliable knowledge. Previous studies show that recording not only final results but also the steps taken during a process can support collaboration, transparency, and innovation that is open and accessible.

The project looks at how documentation can stay flexible, adapt to different manufacturing situations, and be a useful part of the design process. The aim is to create a special way of recording how things are made in the city, working out what makes this good, and knowing what people who make things need.

The main aim of this research is to find out more about the methods, strategies and interests that guide everyday documentation practices. The study does not look at the skills of the people taking part, the quality or quantity of their work, or any private information about their professional activities.

3 Tools and methods for carrying out the studies

Interviews will be done online using tools provided by UVic-UCC. Participants must give permission for their recording and transcript to be saved by signing the consent form. If they do not give permission, the interview will not be conducted. The interviews will last up to 40 minutes and will focus on how people document information and how they manage what they know. Transcriptions will be saved with the participant's name, surname and the name of the organisation they represent. This helps to make sure that the analysis is put into the

right context and that references are correctly attributed. All transcripts and analyses will be published online. Before the study is published, the people who took part will be emailed to let them know, and they'll have the chance to ask for any changes. For observational studies, a responsible person will be chosen at the workplace or space where the study is taking place. This person will collect consent forms from everyone who may be affected by the study. If even one person does not agree to take part, the study will not go ahead in that place. The study will be done in places where people make things, like production sites and artisan workshops. The researcher will collect data manually by taking notes. If short interviews are done during the observation period, recordings may be used for transcription, following the same procedures as the interviews. In this case, each interview will last up to 20 minutes. Any digital tools used will be selected to make sure the data is kept safe and can be permanently deleted. The time spent observing them will be up to five days. The timing and length of the visit will be agreed in advance with the contact person at the organisation. The study will result in a written report containing the information needed to understand the findings. If interviews are included, the same procedures used for interviews will apply. The report may also include information about the company. If the organisation doesn't agree to this, the study won't be conducted. Including the organisation's identity helps to understand the analysis better and makes sure that everything is properly referenced. The report will be published online. Before it is published, the contact person will be emailed to let them know and asked to request any necessary edits.

The diary study will be done in places where people make things, like production sites and artisan workshops. The researcher will not be present. All the study materials will be sent to the people taking part, with instructions on how to complete the diary and how to return the materials at the end of the study period. The study will run for up to two weeks. As with the other methods, the arrangements will be agreed with the contact person at the relevant organisation. The diaries will be collected and shared exactly as they are to make sure the information is correct. Materials will be stored in a place where they can be accessed by anyone. Before it is published, the contact person will get an email to let them know and they can ask for any changes if they need to.

PI will not share the audio recordings. PI will delete them as soon as PI have finished typing out what was said. The recording captures people's voices, so it involves collecting sensitive personal data. Voice recordings are a type of biometric data, which means they can identify a person. So, both the recording and transcription will be done using tools that allow permanent data deletion. Anyone involved in the study, including the PI, must also not use any AI-powered tools that track emotions, summarise content, or perform other actions where data integrity cannot be guaranteed.

4 Information collected

The researcher will not collect information about industrial methods that are protected by patents or subject to non-disclosure agreements. The study doesn't try to understand how specific projects or business activities are carried out. It

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only focuses on how things are documented.

During the study, the researcher will not ask for information about: where you come from; what you think about politics; what religion or beliefs you have; if you are in a trade union; your genes or biometric data; your health; your sex life; or sexual orientation.

5 Selection of participants

Participants will be chosen based on the type of study:

- Interviews – PI will interview people who work in design or engineering, either in academia or in professional practice. These people should have experience with documentation or knowledge management.
- Observational study – This study will involve makers, artisans and design students.
- Diary study – The people taking part in this study are designers and craftspeople.

To find people to take part in the interviews, the PhD student will use two main strategies:

1. Get in touch with people who have worked on the LAUDS Factories project (lauds.eu), where the PhD student is part of a team working on a specific part of the project.
2. Finding people who might want to take part in the project by looking at publications, project websites or by asking people to recommend people they know.

PI will always contact the person directly, or the relevant research group or organisation if we can't find them. The researcher will not use automated tools or mass-mailing systems to recruit people.

6 Benefits and Risks

By taking part in this research, you will help to develop the PhD project. The results of the study, along with earlier research, will help to shape the documentation method being developed for the PhD. Your involvement is important because it makes sure that the research is based on real-life situations and that the results match what practitioners need, not just what is written in academic papers.

The study will not include any sensitive data as exemplified before (see Information Collected). If any such information is shared by accident, it will be removed from all notes, transcripts and other written material to make sure that those data is made public.

Once the study's results have been published, the information you provided, including your name and the name of the organisation you work for, will be made available online. It will not be possible to delete this information, as it will already have been downloaded by others. Before the PI publish any data, you will be asked to check and validate it.

7 Compensation

Participants in this research will not receive any form of payment or insurance. You can take part in the study whenever you want. The researcher will do their best to make the study as short as possible so that it does not get in the way of the participants' work.

8 Confidentiality

Any personal information you share with the researcher, including the consent form, will be kept secret. The researcher will only share the participant's name, surname and affiliation when linked to the study. Any other personal data, will be kept only for as long as is needed to do with the project and stored in secure folders that only the person in charge of the project can see. All your information will be kept private, following the rules of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation). If any photographs are taken,

they will not contain identifiable images of individuals or any information that can't be shared.

9 Right to know the results

The results of the studies will be published online. The analysis can also be used in academic publications and PhD thesis. Participants can ask about the status of their data whenever they like. If their data has already been published, a copy of the publication will be shared with them.

10 Right to refuse or withdraw

You can choose whether or not to take part in the study. If either the person taking part or the researcher feels uncomfortable at any point during the study, they can ask to stop it. All the information gathered will be deleted straight away. This will not have any negative effects for anyone taking part in the study.

Participants can ask for their data to be deleted at any time. When a request is made, the PI will remove all collected, personal and sensitive data from the secured project folders. However, if the collected data has already been published online, you won't be able to delete it, as other people might already be storing it, accessing it, or downloading it. For this reason, all participants will be contacted before any data is published, so they can request edits or ask for their data to be removed. When the deletion process is finished, the PI will tell the participant what will happen to their data.

11 Right to ask questions

Participants can ask questions at any time before, during, or after the study. You can talk about all the information on this sheet, and the PI can explain why the study is being done, what it aims to achieve, and explain the method the researcher is using.

12 Contacts

If you have any questions, need to withdraw, want to know the results or need any information about the study, you can contact the PI, Matteo Subet, at the following email address: matteo.subet@uvic.cat

13 Consent form's signatures

If the form is printed, two identical copies of the informed consent form will be signed. The person taking part will keep one copy, and the researcher will keep the other. If you sign the form digitally, we'll send you a secure link to sign. The researcher will then save the file, and the participant will be able to access and download their own copy.